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IMPACT OF QUALITY OF PERSONNEL AND CURRICULUM CONTENT IN GOAL ATTAINMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL STUDIES COURSE IN FEDERAL UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

Marilyn Unonwa VAL-OSSAI

Department of Business Education, Faculty of Education, Delta State University, Abraka.

Corresponding Author: marilynossai@yahoo.com, +2348036748664

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which quality of personnel and curriculum content would assure the goal attainment of Entrepreneurial Studies Course in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria. Two specific objectives and two research questions guided the study as well as two null hypotheses which were formulated and tested at .05 alpha level. A descriptive survey design was employed for the study. The population of the study was 13,280 comprising 108 lecturers who are involved in entrepreneurial studies and 13,172 level 300 students who had offered entrepreneurial studies in the six federal universities in south-south, Nigeria. The sample size was 455, comprising 80 lecturers and 375 level 300 students who had already offered entrepreneurial studies. This was determined using Krejcie and Morgan formula and Table. Cluster and simple random sampling technique were employed in the study. Each State in the south-south zone was taken as a cluster, from where simple random sampling technique was employed in selecting the respondents for the study. Two instruments developed by the researcher: “Quality Assurance Parameters and the Goal Attainment of Entrepreneurship Studies Programme Questionnaire (QAPGAESP)” and “Entrepreneurial Studies and Students’ Goal Attainment Indices (ESSGAI)” were used for data collection. Simple linear regression was used for data analysis to provide answers to the research questions and to test the null the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The result showed that quality of personnel and curriculum content significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies programme in federal universities in south-south Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended, among others, that Universities in south-south Nigeria should ensure that quality of personnel and curriculum content are fully adopted in the entrepreneurial studies in line with the benchmark of global best practices.

Keywords: Personnel, Curriculum Content, Goal Attainment, Entrepreneurial Studies

Introduction

Education is the compilation and product of many and varied resources. Among these, teachers stand out as a key to realizing the high standards that are increasingly emphasized in schools and school systems across the country. Research has demonstrated a positive effect of good teacher quality to the goal attainment of educational programmes. The university system in the view of Kirimi and Wycliffe (2013) involves the interplay of personnel, infrastructure and curriculum while students are products of such interaction. The quality of academic personnel with respect to entrepreneurial studies influences the quality of skill inculcated to students and the goals attained.

The development of entrepreneurial programme is becoming embedded in policy across Nigeria. Previous research by Ugwoke et al. (2005) has shown the essential role that education plays in the development of such mindsets, and in particular the central role that teachers play in this process. It requires nothing less than a change in the approach to education, emphasizing active learning and the provision of new experiences for students outside the classroom. For many education systems this represents a fundamental shift away from traditional approaches. Teachers are in the middle of these changes. They need to be equipped with the right skills, knowledge and attitudes to be able to provide their students with the new curricula, pedagogies and learning environments that they will need if they are to acquire entrepreneurial competencies.

Universities in South-South Nigeria are required to have teachers with competencies and training in entrepreneurship education to be able to teach entrepreneurial studies. Lecturers are the last post to translate government policies and intentions into practical form and the key factor that determine the quality and success of any curriculum. Akpan (2009) postulated that the success and progress of any educational system depends upon lecturers' number, quality, devotion and commitment. The nature of instructional tasks influences the lecturer's student relationship and interaction, since the communicative functions revolve around the task given.

Mahmood (2013) observed that the quality of personnel (lecturers) consists of teachers academic qualification, quality of teacher training, teaching experiences, pedagogical practices, professional development, mentoring, coaching, subject knowledge, dedication, commitment level and classroom management abilities. The demands made on teachers, school leaders, and teacher educators are increasing and changing. They are called on to play a key role in modernising education. Adeyemi (2010) stated that there exists a significant relationship between the availability of subject lecturers and achievement of skilled entrepreneur. It can therefore be concluded that quality and quantity of lecturers in Nigerian South-South University significantly influence the quality assurance parameter and student skill attainment.

On the other hand, curriculum is one of the most influential and important components in development of entrepreneurial spirit in higher education system. Curriculum plays a significant role in determining the orientations and directions of activities which are carried out in universities and higher education institutions in various forms. In fact, curriculum as the heart and core of academic centers plays a key role in the success or failure of these centers (Lunenburg and Ornstein, 2004). There is, however, no consensus among professionals and experts in this field over the concept of the curriculum (Maleki, 2008). Although this concept has been defined by most scholars by terms and phrases such as 'educational subjects', 'educational content', 'objective performance goals', and 'unpredicted learning experiences' (Nasr et al., 2007, Fathi, 2014), it is certain that the core principle of all educational institutions is not budget but the curriculum which provides a variety of experiences and learning opportunities through which it is possible to achieve students' participation and involvement to accomplish the objectives of higher education. For Long, Street and Shane (1993), curriculum has not emerged to achieve a set of specific goals but to meet the ever-increasing complexities of decision-making in educational institutions. Eisner (1994) believes that curriculum reflects a series of designed educational events in order to anticipate and achieve the learning outcomes for one or more learners.

From this perspective, if curriculum is considered as formal and informal content, a process, and overt and covert training by which the learner acquires the necessary knowledge and skills, and changes his/her attitudes under the guidance of school (Maleki, 2008), it can be said that an entrepreneurial curriculum should include a set of contents and processes through which students will learn concepts, attitudes and entrepreneurial skills and will internalize them. In this context, specifying the role and position of curricular elements in entrepreneurship becomes necessary. According to experts' and

scholars' views, the aforementioned elements can be discussed as components such as objectives, content and learning experiences, teaching and learning methods, assessment methods, teaching space, etc. Anyhow, training entrepreneurship can be done in different ways and by various methods but curriculum is the most important element in it (Gibb, 2005). In fact, the bridge between the university and the student is curriculum. Students, as a part of their major role, learn how to use theories of entrepreneurship through the acquisition of attitudes and ideas and how to put them into practice. Based on this definition, curriculum experts classify the main elements of curriculum as objectives, content and learning experiences, teaching and learning methods, assessment methods, teaching space, time, equipment and learners' teaming. Therefore, this research studies the place of entrepreneurial studies programme curriculum in different dimensions (objectives, content, teaching and learning strategies, assessment methods, and management practice) at University. Most research in this area has been conducted on issues such as small businesses, characteristics of entrepreneurs, and corporate and independent entrepreneurship, and has paid less attention to entrepreneurial curriculum, objectives, content, and teaching methods of entrepreneurship (Ahmadzadeh, 2006). The results and findings of this study can be used by policy makers of higher education in order to help them design and develop curricula and entrepreneurship education, and thereby help expand this area vastly. Results of this research will also help universities identify their potentials to become entrepreneurial universities.

Furthermore, Philip (2016) averred that the development in students of broadly defined competencies or capabilities, such as critical and creative thinking, depends on the integration of three broad learning domains: knowledge, skills and values. Central to curriculum change is the notion of quality. The aforementioned questions are all related to this notion. But what does 'quality' mean in a curriculum context? What is the quality framework within which curriculum developers can set goals, develop and implement change processes, and eventually gauge their success? Some useful indicators of a quality curriculum have to do with its relevance, consistency, practicality, effectiveness and sustainability.

Curriculum is, in the simplest terms, a description of what, why, how and when students should learn. The curriculum is not, of course, an end in itself. Rather, it seeks both to achieve worthwhile and useful learning outcomes for students, and to realize a range of societal demands and government policies. It is in and through the curriculum that key economic, political, social and cultural questions about the aims, purposes, content and processes of education are resolved.

According to Philip (2016), the policy statement and technical document that represent the curriculum reflect also a broader political and social agreement about what a society deems of most worth – that which is of sufficient importance to pass on to its children. A principal objective of a quality curriculum is, in a fair and inclusive manner, to enable students to acquire and develop the knowledge, skills and values, and the associated capabilities and competencies, to lead meaningful and productive lives. Key indicators of curriculum success include the quality of the learning achieved by students, and how effectively students use that learning for their personal, social, physical, cognitive, moral, psychological and emotional development. A quality curriculum maximizes the potential for the effective enhancement of learning. Underlying this paper is the premise that educational quality should be understood primarily in terms of the quality of student learning, which in turn depends to a great extent on the quality of teaching. Of prime importance in this is the fact that good teaching and learning are greatly enhanced by the quality, relevance and effectiveness of the curriculum.

Statement of the Problem

Quality assurance is designed to prove and improve the quality of an institution's methods, educational processes and products. Quality assurance involves series of operational techniques and activities which include all actions taken for

academic standards to be met. Academic standards are public statements about what students should learn and what students should be able to do. Standards describe the goals of schooling, the destinations at which students should arrive at the end of the course. Nigeria has the benchmark for minimum academic standards (BMAS) but the standard does not prescribe how to get the students to the destination. That is determined by the curriculum. The autonomy of universities that allows that universities plan their curriculum made room for entrepreneurship education to be introduced by National Universities Commission (NUC) into the Nigeria universities curriculum with a benchmark. However, to meet the prescribed standards, quality assurance parameters are put in place. The challenge with the BMAS is not primarily what is in this standard or what has been left out, but in the role the quality assurance parameters play in ensuring the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies programme across Nigerian universities. To ensure that the standards are met and that universities even go beyond the standards, the NUC follows up with accreditation exercise in universities in the country. The whole process of accreditation is to ensure quality assurance and defaulting universities are sanctioned. Failure of universities to ensure that the quality assurance parameters are reviewed and goals attained for entrepreneurial studies programme will lead to forfeiture of accreditation and worse still, students and graduates will be denied the opportunity of acquiring entrepreneurship skills, which defeats the purpose of the programme in the first place.

If the universities fail to identify the core quality assurance parameters, then, it becomes challenging focusing on the key issues that determine successful programme goal attainment as well as for monitoring and evaluation of entrepreneurial programme. It is argued that the impact of entrepreneurial studies programme on the post-training career choice and practice by students assure the teaching and assessment methodologies used in delivering entrepreneurship education lessons, the availability of training resources (facilities), the entrepreneurial studies curriculum itself as well as the level of supervision given to students. All these factors make up the quality assurance parameters. Thus, inability to follow up with the quality assurance parameters results in failure in attaining the goals of entrepreneurial studies in Nigerian universities. As important as the introduction of entrepreneurial studies into university curriculum is to the nation, and how significant the programme is to changing the narrative of Nigerian students towards job creation, little or no study is cited by the researcher on how quality assurance parameters would assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies programme in Nigerian universities. Policy makers in education sector are therefore left in the dark with regards to how quality assurance parameters would assure the goal attainment of this all important programme. This study therefore seeks to ascertain the extent to which quality of personnel and curriculum content assure the goal attainment of Entrepreneurial Studies Course in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to ascertain the extent to which quality of personnel and curriculum content assure the goal attainment of Entrepreneurial Studies Course in Federal Universities in South-South Nigeria. Specifically; the study sought to:

1. determine the extent to which quality of personnel assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.
2. determine the extent to which quality of curriculum content assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated based on the research objectives to guide the study.

1. To what extent would quality of personnel assure goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria?
2. To what extent would quality of curriculum content assure goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at .05 level of significance.

HO1: quality of personnel does not significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

HO2: quality of curriculum content does not significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design. Survey design was chosen for this study as it is most appropriate for gathering information. This was considered suitable since data will be required in their natural distribution in the population. The study was conducted in the South-South zone of Nigeria. It involved federal universities offering entrepreneurship programmes in South-South Zone of Nigeria. South-South Nigeria comprises six States, namely Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers States. South-South Nigeria also comprises of five federal universities namely University of Uyo, Uyo, University of Calabar, Calabar, University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State and University of Benin, Edo State.

The population of the study was 13280 respondents comprising 108 lecturers who are involved in entrepreneurial studies and 13172 level three hundred students who offer entrepreneurial studies in federal universities in South-South Nigeria. The sample size was 455, comprising 80 lecturers and 375 level 300 students who had already offered entrepreneurial studies. This was determined using Krejcie and Morgan formula and table. Furthermore, multistage sampling was employed for the determining the sample of the study. Cluster sampling is used in the distribution of universities. Each of the participating universities was taken as a cluster, from where simple random sampling was adopted to select the required number of participants from each university.

The researcher developed two sets of instruments for the study titled, “Quality Assurance Parameters and Goal Attainment of Entrepreneurial Studies Course Questionnaire (QAPGAESC)” and “Entrepreneurial Studies and Students’ Goal Attainment Indices (ESSGAI)”. The structured questionnaire had a category of four point rating scale ranging from Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) relative to the variables under investigation. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha. The coefficients gave an average value of .85 and .86 for QAPGAESC and ESSGAI respectively.

In answering the research questions and testing the null hypotheses, the regression analysis was employed. The regression coefficients (β , r , and R^2) were used to answer the research questions and the null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent would quality of personnel assure goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of Regression Coefficient Test for Assuring Goal Attainment from Quality of Personnel

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	R	R ²
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.582	.153			
	Quality of Personnel	.564	.044	.589	0.589*	0.346

*High extent of assurance

Data in Table 1 gives the summary of the regression test for how quality of personnel would assure goal attainment. The result of analysis shows that for every unit rise in quality of personnel, goal attainment increases by 0.564. That is, every time the quality of personnel is enhanced, goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course by students is enhanced. The result also shows that the R-value of 0.589, indicating a high extent of assurance of quality personnel on goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course. The Table further revealed that the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.346, indicating that 34.6% of goal attainment is assured by quality of personnel.

Research Question 2: To what extent would quality of curriculum content assure goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies courses in federal universities in south-south Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of Regression Coefficient Test for Assuring Goal Attainment from Quality of Curriculum Content

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	R	R ²
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.434	.197			
	Quality of Curriculum Content	.571	.057	.495	0.678*	0.453

*High extent of assurance

Data in Table 2 shows the summary of the regression coefficients after analysis to determine how quality of curriculum content assures goal attainment (GA). The result shows that at every unit rise in quality of curriculum, Goal Attainment increases by 0.571. This indicates that the quality of the curriculum can be used to assure Goal Attainment for entrepreneurial studies course in South-South Universities to a high extent. The coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.453, indicating that 45.3% of goal attainment is assured by quality of curriculum content.

Research Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Quality of personnel does not significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of Regression test of Significance for Assuring Goal Attainment from Quality of Personnel

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	Fcal	Sig.of F	Decision
1	Regression	26.452	1	26.452	34.824	.002	Significant*
	Residual	344.097	453	.760			
	Total	370.549	454				

*significant @ .002 (p< .05)

Result on Table 3 gives the summary of the regression analysis for test of significance. The result shows that at 0.05 level of significance, the probability level is .002. Since the probability value is less than the level of significance (p< .05), the result is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that quality of personnel does significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis 2

H02: Quality of curriculum content does not significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of Regression test of Significance for Assuring Goal Attainment from Quality of Curriculum Content

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	Fcal	Sig.of F	Decision
1	Regression	37.631	1	37.631	34.444	0.002	Significant*
	Residual	494.906	453	1.093			
	Total	532.536	454				

*significant @ .002 (p< .05)

Data in table 4 shows the summary of the regression analysis for test of significance on how quality of curriculum content assures goal attainment. The result gives the calculated f-ratio at 34.444 and the significance of F, that is the probability value (p-value) at .002. Since the probability value of .002 is less than the level of significance (.05), the result is statistically significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, quality of curriculum content does significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

Following the results of research questions and null hypotheses tested in this study, the findings are discussed under the following sub headings.

Quality of Personnel and the Goal Attainment of Entrepreneurial Studies Course

Result of the analysis of research question shows that every time the quality of personnel is enhanced, goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies by students is enhanced. The result also shows that the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.589, indicating a moderate positive correlation between quality of personnel and goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies. The result reveals that the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.346, indicating that 34.6% change in goal attainment is as a result of quality of personnel. The corresponding hypothesis test shows that quality of personnel does significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria. This is necessarily so because, the teachers are essential factor in the delivery of instruction to students, regardless of the mode of instruction. Lecturers are the front-line

service providers in university education. Good lecturers do more than teach curriculum content: they inspire and enthuse their students while also serving as role models, in terms of attitudes and social relationships as they model behaviours. The role of the entrepreneurial teachers is to promote the acquisition of technical skills as well as scientific knowledge that will help the students develop employability skills as well as become self-reliant, participative and responsible citizens. This findings is corroborated by Mahmood (2013) which found that teachers' quality consists of teachers academic qualification, quality of teacher training, teaching experiences, pedagogical practices, professional development, mentoring, coaching, subject knowledge, dedication, commitment level and classroom management abilities. Furthermore, Adeyemi (2010) averred that there exists a significant relationship between the availability of subject lecturers and achievement of skilled entrepreneur. It can therefore be concluded that quality and quantity of lecturers in Nigerian South-South University significantly influence the quality assurance parameter and student skill attainment.

Quality of Curriculum Content and the Goal Attainment of Entrepreneurial Studies Course

Findings from the research question shows that the quality of the curriculum can be used to assure goal attainment for entrepreneurial studies course in South-South Universities to a great extent. Furthermore, the correlation coefficient shows that the r-value is 0.678, indicating a high positive relationship between quality of curriculum content and goal attainment. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.453, indicating that 45.3% change in goal attainment is as a result of quality of curriculum content. The equivalent hypothesis test shows that quality of curriculum content does significantly assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria. This is so as it is the curriculum that determines to a large extent whether education is inclusive and self-reliant, thus, playing a significant role in ensuring that provision and attainment is equitable. It is the curriculum that provides the structure for the provision of quality learning, especially where teachers might be under-qualified and inexperienced, their classrooms under-resource, and their students lacking the prior frameworks within which to situate their learning. It is also the curriculum that articulates both the competencies necessary for lifelong learning and the competencies needed for entrepreneurship skills development. These findings are in consonance with the work of Lunenburg and Ornstein (2004), who revealed that a quality curriculum maximizes the potential for the effective enhancement of learning. Curriculum plays a significant role in determining the orientations and directions of activities which are carried out in universities and higher education institutions in various forms. In fact, curriculum as the heart and core of academic centres plays a key role in the success or failure of these centres. This finding is also in line with Maleki (2008) who found that entrepreneurial curriculum should include a set of contents and processes through which students will learn concepts, attitudes and entrepreneurial skills and will internalize them. In this context, specifying the role and position of curricular elements in entrepreneurship becomes necessary.

Conclusion

As important as the introduction of entrepreneurial studies into university curriculum is to the nation, and how significant the course is to changing the narrative of Nigerian students towards job creation, little or no study is cited by the researcher on how quality assurance parameters would assure the goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in Nigerian universities. Policy makers in education sector were therefore left in the dark with regards to how quality assurance parameters would assure the goal attainment of this all important course. From the findings in this study, it is concluded that quality of personnel and curriculum content assure goal attainment of entrepreneurial studies course in federal universities in south-south Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. University administrators across south-south, Nigeria should try and ensure that the staff involved in entrepreneurial studies are qualified and possess the requisite knowledge and skills in entrepreneurship.
- ii. University administrators across south-south, Nigeria should also try to train and retrain academic and support staff on new trends in business, innovation and technology that supports entrepreneurship training and skills development.

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